

A Brief Review on Functionalities and Aspects of DC Microgrid

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ABSTRACT

In the present era, the traditional electrical power system is facing serious challenges arising out of tremendous escalation of power demand associated with deficiency of quality power required by the huge digital loads of present day, dictated by increasing population globally. Depletion of fossil fuels and reduction in carbon emission related to environment concerns are two major issues also against sole dependence on centralized generation of fossil fuel based brown power. These factors acted as driving forces in the establishment of microgrid concept in electrical power scenario. A revolutionary change in electrical grid thus has been achieved through the inception microgrid in terms of decentralized generation of green (eco-friendly) power, bidirectional flow of energy and data, and integrated control. The aim of this paper is to present a brief review on functionalities and aspects of direct current (dc) microgrid in light of present development. First, it discusses on definition, components, classification, and configuration details of microgrid. Then, major aspects of DC microgrid like, voltage control, power management have been discussed and lastly challenges faced by it are added to depict the overall functionality.

KEYWORDS- *microgrid, renewable energy sources, classification, dc microgrid, voltage control, power management.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The traditional electrical power system, consisting of limited number of power stations, generating centralized unidirectional flow of electricity, has been developed through three key foundations viz., generation, transmission, and distribution and thus, needs long distance transmission at high voltage which suffers from transmission loss, huge maintenance cost, insufficient supply of quality power, causing public inconvenience (Yoldas et al., 2017). The conventional power generation is fossil fuel based and these resources are limited in nature and produce Green House Gas and thus imposing potential threat for climate change issue globally (Elavarasan et al., 2020). Today's consumers of electricity, require quality power at a reasonable cost in an environmentally susceptible way which is out of scope of traditional grid based conventional power system. In order to address the said problem a distributed generation (DG), RERs based microgrids (MG), and energy storage systems (ESS) have emerged in recent decades. MG acts locally, as an alternative grid incorporated with distributed energy resources (DERs) that include renewable energy sources (RES) at a large scale, which are inexhaustible in nature and generate eco-friendly green power (Wu et al., 2024). MG is capable of providing independent generation, integrated control, and environmental benefits at an affordable cost and hence are having significant importance in the future electrical power system. (Wu et al., 2024).

It facilitates realization of smart grid through penetration of massive DERs. MGs can operate in grid-connected mode or islanded mode, based on the operation policy (Al-Ismail et al., 2024). Depending on the type of voltage in the point of common coupling (PCC), MGs can be distinguished as alternating current (AC) or direct current (DC) MG (Dragičević et al., 2016). It has been observed since the last two decades that, DC MGs are gaining increasing importance (Al-Ismail et al., 2024, Dragičević et al., 2016). Hence emphasis has been given on functionalities of DC MG in this paper.

The rest of this paper is organised as follows: Section 2 presents review on MG functionalities based on definition, components, classification, and configuration details. Major aspects of DC MG functionalities like, voltage control strategies in detail, power management techniques and thereafter challenges faced by MG along with suitable recommendations are reviewed in section 3 and section 4 respectively.

2. MICROGRID FUNCTIONALITIES

2.1. Definition of Microgrid

Microgrids are a small scale of low voltage power grids used for local distribution within clearly defined electrical boundaries which are controllable and consist of a set of distributed products such as wind turbines, diesel generators, fuel cells, photovoltaic systems, energy storage, and load systems, and can be used in two forms of grid connection or islanding (Wu et al., 2024).

2.2. Components of Microgrid

The main components of microgrid include: DERs, energy storage system (ESS), Diesel Generator (DG) set and Controller unit. The DERs may be different types of renewable energy sources like solar, wind, biomass etc. The ESS and DG set act as a back-up power source as per requirement. ESS are mainly battery, supercapacitor, flywheel energy storage etc., (Al-Ismail et al., 2024).

2.3. Classification of Microgrid

A comparative approach as mentioned below in Table:1 (Wu et al., 2024, Dragičević et al., 2016)

Table 1. Classification of Microgrid

Classification Basis	Types	Description
Size	Small	Power rating ≤ 10 MW. Suitable for home loads, remote areas, and small regions.
	Medium	Power rating ≤ 100 MW. Suitable for industrial and commercial loads.
	Large	Power rating ≤ 1000 MW. Suitable for industrial and commercial loads.
Control approaches	Centralized	Single controller manages all components. Low reliability, low scalability, high complexity.
	Decentralized	Multiple controllers operate independently. High reliability, high scalability, medium complexity.
	Distributed	Controllers share information to improve performance. Medium reliability, medium scalability, low complexity.
Power supply	AC microgrid	Connected to an AC power source. No additional control needed. Can be single-phase, grounded three-phase, or ungrounded three-phase. Operates at high, low, or standard frequencies.
	DC microgrid	Relies on DC electricity for distribution and storage. High efficiency, suitable for remote/off-grid areas.
	Hybrid microgrid	Combines AC and DC microgrids. Uses renewable energy sources, fossil fuel generators, and energy storage systems. Offers increased flexibility and reliability.

2.4. Configuration of Microgrid

Based on its operating mode, MG can be configured as follows (as shown in Figure 1.)

2.4.1. Islanding mode

In that case the microgrid can operate independently and is not connected to the main grid. This operating mode is used to provide electrical power nearest to the grid or in the remote areas or island where the

conventional electricity cannot be transmitted to meet up the load demand.

2.4.2. Grid-connected mode:

In that case the microgrid is connected to the utility grid and can exchange electricity with main grid through the point of common coupling to the grid and will be able to supply the electricity into main grid and take electricity when there is power shortage.

Figure1. Operating modes of microgrid (Wu et al., 2024)

3. MICROGRID MAIN ASPECTS

DC MGs rely on DC electricity to distribute and store energy. They are designed to provide reliable power, often in remote or off-grid areas. (Wu et al., 2024). As comparing the performance, DC MG is better than the AC MG in terms of power management and voltage control techniques. By design, DC microgrids may keep their voltage at a constant level, improving stability, reliability, compatibility with DC loads, and simplified integration of energy storage devices. Again, as the DC system does not include reactive power, hence less complex voltage control techniques are required for it, and thereby improving stability and reliability of the grid is achieved while used to power up DC loads. Therefore, DC MGs have higher system efficiency, lower cost, and system size (Al-Ismail et al., 2024, Dragičević et al., 2016). In view of all these aspects of DC MG, voltage control and power management of this are discussed in the following sections.

3.1. Voltage Control of DC Microgrid

In a DC microgrid, the control of DERs and ESS units generally aim to control bus voltage without any fluctuation under steady-state conditions. The basic three control strategies are already mentioned in Table 1. All these types of control schemes come under the basis of Co-ordinated control scheme (Dragičević et al., 2016). A popular control scheme called ‘Adaptive droop control’ (under Decentralized control) is discussed below along with control schematics (Figure 2.). Another concept of centralized control has been presented in Figure 4. along with description in brief.

3.2. Adaptive droop control

An adaptive droop control is proposed as shown in Figure 2, (Al-Ismail et al., 2024), which is regulated and compensated by two PI controllers. One adaptive PI controller is utilized to perform droop control for current shearing deviation elimination, another adaptive PI controller is adopted to adjust the DC bus voltage of the microgrid by modifying the droop curve of the microgrid as shown in the Figure 3. The sliding mode control circuit is applied to control the output voltage and input current

Figure 2. Adaptive droop control (Han et al., 2019)

of each converter synchronously (Han et al., 2019). The adaptive PI controller is adopted to adjust the droop coefficient to eliminate the current sharing deviation (e_{ci}) as shown in equation (1), in each unit of the DC microgrid:

$$e_{ci} = i_{oi} - i_{MG}(i_i^{nom} / \sum_{j=1}^n j_j^{nom}) \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Where, i_{oi} is the output current of the i th converter, i_{MG} is the load current, and i_i^{nom} is the nominal current of the i th converter, n is the number of converters and another PI converter compensates the DC bus voltage of the control microgrid by moving the droop curve. Hence the fast dynamic response and good robustness can be realized (Han et al., 2019). Furthermore, the conventional droop control can be enhanced by adjusting the curve-coefficient, which could be adjusted from no load to full load. For simplicity the conventional droop control in equation (2) is replaced by the equation (3).

$$V_o = V^* - r_d \cdot i_o \dots \dots \dots (2)$$

$$V_o = V^* - \sum_{n=1}^N r_n \cdot i_o^n \dots \dots \dots (3)$$

Where, V_o and i_o are the output voltage and current, v^* is the no-load voltage set point, and the droop coefficient r_d in equation (3) is the sum of the N th power functions of the current i , r_n is the proportional coefficient of the droop coefficient of each segment output.

As shown from the above characteristics, the red line is the conventional linear droop curve and the blue line is the nonlinear droop curve. The nonlinear droop formula can be written as

$$V_0 = \begin{cases} V^* - a_1 i_0^2 - b_1 i_0 & 0 < i_0 \leq i_{op} \\ V^* - a_2 i_0^2 - b_2 i_0 - c & i_{op} < i_0 < i_{omax} \end{cases}$$

Figure 3. Conventional droop control and nonlinear droop control curve design (Han et al., 2019)

Where i_{op} is output current of the converter, i_{max} is the maximum output current of the converter and the accuracy of current sharing among inverter is guaranteed by the configuration of the curve parameters a_1 , a_2 , b_1 , b_2 , c . Therefore, the division point i_{op} is selected according to the low range of the low droop coefficient condition, where dividing the function into two parts is the most efficient, and the current sharing precision could be ensured.

3.3. Centralized Voltage Control

Centralize controller referring to DC MG, describes a control structure in which all the individual generators and load units are managed and monitored from a single location. By setting up in this way, all components of the microgrids can coordinate and make decisions with ease because of the central role played by the communication link. The conceptual block diagram of the centralized controller is provided in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Centralized voltage control (Al-Ismail et al., 2024)

3.4. DC Microgrid Power Management

In DC MG, power management is essential for optimum utilization of resources, grid stability and energy distribution (Al-Ismail et al., 2024). For DC MG monitoring energy resources, ESS and loads is essential to avoid power imbalances and voltage dip in DC bus bar. Different strategies like droop control, hierarchical control etc. that dynamically allocate and distribute power from source to load are employed for power management of DC MG. Additionally, demand response, energy forecasting and optimization algorithms allow DC MGs to adapt to changes demand. Several components of the DC MGs, such as DERs, ESS, AC/DC loads, and smart homes, take part in power balancing. Conventional methods, artificial intelligence, Metaheuristic optimization) and other methods are implemented to balance power within the DC MG systems (Al-Ismail et al., 2024).

4. CHALLENGES AND RECOMMENDATIONS OF MICROGRID

4.1 Challenges

Major challenges faced by MG system are:

i. Operational:

While functioning as a source or load, switching an MG system from grid connected mode to islanding mode causes power imbalance and voltage fluctuation (Saeed et al., 2021).

ii. Compatibility:

A microgrid consists of various components, including diesel generator set, micro-turbine, fuel cell, RESs, inverters, communication system, control software and so on, which differ in generation capacity, shutdown time, operational cost and efficiency, energy storage charging and discharging rates, as well as control and communication constraints (Saeed et al., 2021). Variation of output power delivered by these intermittent sources creates a power sharing imbalance.

iii. Uncertainty Associated with Integration of renewable generation:

The diverse characteristics of weather may cause several major challenges associated with uncertainty for integration of RES to the main grid. Therefore, the output of these resources becomes unpredictable and can vary abruptly and frequently and imposes challenges on maintaining stable microgrid operation (Yoldas et al., 2017).

4.2 Recommendations: The recommendations are as follows:

i. Advanced Monitoring and Control Strategies:

In order to maintain constant voltage and required power, DC MGs must be able to detect islanding promptly and reliably and advanced monitoring technologies are required for that. ESS and FACTS devices provide suitable solutions to the problems arising during this transition (Saeed et al., 2021).

ii. Modelling and Simulation in DC Microgrids:

The challenge arising out of interaction of multiple components with varying characteristics, can be overcome with ESS, advanced coordination control, backup power and grid connection, local load control, and accurate AI-based forecasting and control (Al-Ismail et al., 2024). Precise modelling is essential for developing efficient control strategies and making reliable predictions about system behaviour.

Figure 5. Installed Renewable Energy capacity in India as on 29th February 2020 (Elavarasan et al., 2020)

5. CONCLUSIONS

The emergence of microgrids in electrical power sector has significant functional benefits over the conventional system in the following ways: reduction in carbon emission, plug-and-play capabilities for switching between grid connected and islanding modes, helping sustainable operation of the local grid, thus improving overall power systems quality. Despite many merits of microgrids, there are major challenges lying in the grid integration through DERs and implementation of protection scheme for stable functioning of it, owing to which this field has become a hot spot of research work presently. India Govt. has adopted many policies to promote renewable energy generation and distribution deploying MGs. Figure 5 shows the total installed capacity of RE in India. The data has been adopted from the Ministry of New and Renewable Energy (MNRE) report, which was uploaded on 29th February 2020 (Elavarasan et al., 2020)

This paper reviews mainly on the major functionalities of MG, with an emphasis on DC MG in brief. There are many other important aspects of MGs, like stability criteria, communication system, protection scheme and advanced forecasting techniques, to illustrate the entire functionalities of the MG system, which are out of scope of this paper owing to the space limitation and may be focused on later.

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